

MOTCAM in XGAIN: AI-Powered Object Detection for 5G-Enabled Drones

Writers: Kurdman Rasol, Claudio Carballo, August Betzler, Joan Josep Aleixendri

Organisation: Fundació i2CAT

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Enhancing Drone Operations with MOTCAM in XGAIN

Building upon the foundational work detailed in our previous blog on the **Testing and Validation of Use Case (UC) 1 – A Rural Drone Centre**, this article explores a key advancement in the XGAIN project [1]: the integration of Mobile Object Tracking Camera (MOTCAM), a real-time object detection solution, within our 5G-enabled drone operations. With rural connectivity challenges in mind, XGAIN continues to push the boundaries of innovation, demonstrating the transformative potential of edge computing, AI-based analytics, and 5G networks for remote environments.

MOTCAM: Object Detection at the Edge

MOTCAM is an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven object detection system optimized for real-time video analysis, originally developed under the PAI-Mobility project [2] and now adapted for XGAIN. Within the project, a stripped-down version of MOTCAM is deployed, focusing primarily on object detection capabilities to support precision agriculture, environmental monitoring, and security applications in rural areas [3]. The MOTCAM system is modular and scalable, comprising the following key components:

- **Video Pre-processing:** Calibration tools for camera distortion correction.
- **Object Detection:** Deep learning models trained in COCO classes to identify people, vehicles, and other objects.
- **Tracking and Geo-localization:** Advanced tracking using homography transformation to determine object positions in real-world coordinates accurately.
- **Trajectory Prediction and Dynamics:** Motion tracking and velocity estimation with Kalman filters.
- **Visualization and Event Analysis:** Real-time visualization overlays, including OpenStreetMap integration for location-based insights.

In XGAIN, MOTCAM delivers real-time object detection, identifying humans and vehicles directly from video feeds. With edge AI processing on a Jetson Orin device (also tested on an Intel NUC with less performance), it ensures low-latency analysis without reliance on cloud computing. Its 5G integration enables seamless video streaming from the drone to the edge node, supporting uninterrupted detection and tracking for real-time applications.

Figure 1. Real-time object detection with MOTCAM, identifying humans and vehicles in a rural environment using edge AI processing

Advanced Drone Hardware for 5G-Enabled Object Detection

The XGAIN project leverages cutting-edge drone technology to enable real-time AI-powered object detection with MOTCAM. This setup's core is the DJI Matrice 300 RTK, an industry-standard drone known for its rugged design, long flight endurance, and precision navigation [4]. To enhance connectivity, the drone is equipped with a DJI E-Port Development Kit, allowing seamless integration with extreme edge computing devices, mounted on the drone itself. A Raspberry Pi 4 serves as a lightweight compute node, acting as a relay for transmitting video streams over 5G networks and other lightweight processing tasks. A 5G mini router also ensures fast and stable data transmission, enabling uninterrupted real-time processing at the edge. These components, combined with Persualdrone's¹ expertise in drone operations, ensure that XGAIN's 5G-enabled AI solution can operate reliably in rural and remote environments.

¹ <https://persualdrone.com/>

Figure 2. 5G-enabled drone hardware setup [5]

Testing MOTCAM with 5G-Enabled Drone Operations

From Lab to Field: Validating the Setup

To integrate MOTCAM into 5G-enabled drone operations, the XGAIN team conducted a series of validation tests at the 5G Coebre Lab in Mora la Nova, Catalonia, as part of the use case implemented by i2CAT. This site offers an indoor flight space, ensuring a controlled environment for real-time video streaming and object detection validation. However, the demonstration setup followed a multi-phase validation approach to ensure system reliability before deployment in real-world scenarios. The validation process began with controlled lab testing of the 5G-enabled infrastructure, where key performance metrics such as network latency, throughput, and detection accuracy were measured under stable conditions. This phase allowed for issue identification and resolution before real-world implementation.

Figure 3. MOTCAM validation for 5G-enabled drone operations at the 5G CoEbre Lab

Further, several lab tests were conducted before deploying MOTCAM in real-world drone operations to ensure optimal performance and system stability. One such test involved streaming video using Open Broadcaster Software (OBS) and the Real-Time Streaming Protocol (RTSP) Server plugin on a laptop setup. The results showed good video quality with minimal CPU usage, as the system avoided re-encoding the video stream. However, a delay of around 1–1.5 seconds was observed between the OBS video and the RTSP stream retrieved by FFmpeg. These controlled tests provided valuable insights into network latency and streaming efficiency, helping fine-tune the system before integration into 5G-enabled drone operations.

Figure 4. Lab tests optimized MOTCAM's performance for 5G-enabled drone operations

On the other hand, the streaming pipeline setup utilized Raspberry Pi 4, Jetson Orin, and Intel NUC as edge computing nodes, enabling real-time video transmission over 5G using RTSP. This configuration ensured seamless playback with minimal frame loss, a crucial factor for accurate real-time object detection. To assess AI performance, MOTCAM's deep neural networks were deployed on Jetson Orin, achieving 16 FPS with GPU acceleration. Object detection algorithms were tested on both static and moving video feeds, with comparisons between re-encoded and non-re-encoded video streams to optimize processing efficiency.

The 5G network's impact on video transmission was also analyzed by measuring latency and bandwidth fluctuations, ensuring stable and reliable connectivity. Buffer settings in FFmpeg were fine-tuned to prevent frame drops, guaranteeing that the system operated efficiently, and the video transmission rate harmonized with the pace of the 5G transmission. The results demonstrated that the real-time object detection pipeline achieved low latency (~315ms end-to-end processing time) and high accuracy across multiple object types, validating its feasibility for AI-powered drone analytics in remote areas.

Next Steps: Live Demonstration in 2025

With successful validation in the lab, the next step is a full-scale live demonstration scheduled for April 2025. In this event, a 5G-connected drone will be deployed to stream live video to an edge computing server, where MOTCAM's AI will be used to demonstrate that a disoriented, lost or injured person (e.g., lost hiker or an elderly person) can be easily detected. As such, MOTCAM will be acting as a support tool for the drone operation.

A critical aspect of this demonstration is the role of Persualdrone, which will oversee the drone's flight operations and integration with the 5G network. Their expertise ensures the drone operates efficiently in real-world conditions, optimizing flight paths and maintaining stable connectivity for AI-powered object detection.

This demonstration will serve as a key milestone in the XGAIN project, showcasing the capabilities of 5G-enabled drones to stakeholders in rural connectivity. The final goal is to establish a scalable blueprint for rural drone operation centers, proving how 5G and AI-powered analytics can help bridge the digital divide and empower local communities with cutting-edge technology.

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